

EXAMINING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIGITAL COMPETENCE AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract

Globally, information and communication technologies (ICT) is now embedded in everyday life worldwide, including education, work, leisure, civic engagement, and social interaction. As digital access and tools continue to expand, digital literacy competencies have become increasingly essential. This study examines the relationship between university students' digital competence and English language proficiency. Using an internationally informed framework, digital competence was assessed across five dimensions: information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, digital safety, and artificial intelligence and digital ethics. Data were collected from 357 Mandakh University students through a self-assessment questionnaire administered via Microsoft Forms. Factor and regression analyses were used to validate the dimensions and identify influencing factors. The findings show that students' overall digital competence was moderate to good, with an average score of 3.82. Communication and collaboration was the strongest dimension, while digital safety was the weakest. Regression results confirmed that English proficiency and information technology experience significantly influenced all five dimensions of digital competence. However, many students reported difficulty understanding English-language software instructions, learning materials, and online resources. The study suggests that improving English proficiency and increasing practical technology experience can strengthen students' overall digital competence.

Keywords: digital literacy practices; usages of English language, tertiary students.

Introduction

As technology continues to advance rapidly, evaluating the extent to which students are prepared for learning, employment, and daily life in a digital environment has become increasingly important. The growing need to assess citizens' ICT-related competencies in an increasingly digital world is reflected in global and regional policy frameworks. For example, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals include measures of youth and adults' ICT skills under Indicator 4.4.1 (UN, 2017), while digital competence is recognized as one of the eight key competencies for lifelong learning in the European framework. According to the report "An International Perspective on Digital Literacy", preparing students to use ICT in the workplace and promoting the responsible, ethical, and safe use of digital devices, including cyber-safety, were frequently and explicitly reflected in national plans and policies, appearing in 25 countries (2023). Digital competence refers to the ability to use emerging technologies effectively and purposefully in various areas of life, including learning, work, and leisure. It includes not only the necessary skills and knowledge, but also responsible, active participation in digital environments. Digital competence, as defined in DigComp 2.2, involves the confident, critical, and responsible use of digital technologies for learning, work, and social participation. It includes five areas: information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, safety, and problem-solving. Previous studies show that digital competence supports students' learning engagement, academic performance, and research skills; however, research has mainly focused on overall digital competence, with limited attention to digital learning competence in specific educational

contexts. Digital proficiency can significantly enhance language teaching and learning by providing students with access to authentic language materials, interactive activities, and opportunities for communication and collaboration with native speakers and peers. Furthermore, integrating digital competence into language instruction enables teachers to design more personalized, learner-centered experiences that address students' individual needs, interests, and learning goals (Jiafan Cao 1, 2023).

Second language (L2) digital literacy refers to a complex and integrated set of cognitive and technical skills that enables individuals to access, understand, evaluate, and reinterpret online information accurately in order to construct new knowledge. More importantly, it involves the ability to navigate digital environments, locate relevant information, communicate effectively, and critically evaluate and synthesize information presented in multiple formats and language-specific texts. However, students' L2 digital literacy skills have received limited attention and are often treated as if they are already established. The rapid growth of digital resources and the increasing use of digital libraries have become important supports for second language acquisition (SLA), encouraging EFL students to move beyond traditional paper-based materials and engage more actively with digital formats (Alsmari, 2021). In terms of the theoretical framework, task-technology fit (TTF) explains technology adoption through the alignment between task requirements and technological capabilities. Developed by Goodhue and Thompson (1995), the model suggests that effective outcomes occur when technology supports the intended learning tasks and meets users' needs (Jimmy K. N. Macharia, 2026).

Literature review

The IEA's International Computer and Information Literacy Study 2023 (ICILS 2023) examined students' ability to use information and communication technology (ICT) effectively for various purposes beyond basic use. Building on the 2013 and 2018 cycles, it tracks the development of digital literacy skills over time and explores the contexts that influence students' learning and achievement (2023). Nuha Abdullah Alsmari investigated the relationship between EFL students' second language (L2) digital literacy skills and strategies, their self-efficacy, and their English proficiency levels. The study involved 93 Saudi undergraduate students majoring in English at Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University. Participants were surveyed to examine both their level of English proficiency and their perceived ability to use three major domains of digital literacy skills. This study is relevant because it highlights the role of digital literacy as an important factor in EFL learning and suggests that students' confidence in using digital tools may be connected to their language development (Alsmari, 2021). Alec I. Kennedy (Alec I. Kennedy, 2023) and colleagues reported that, in most countries, students with an immigrant background scored significantly lower in both computer and information literacy (CIL) and computational thinking (CT) than their non-immigrant peers. In contrast, students who usually spoke the language of the assessment at home tended to achieve significantly higher scores in both CIL and CT across the majority of countries. Yafeng Song (2025) found that digital learning competence positively influenced undergraduates' academic achievement, based on data from 312 students. The study also reported higher achievement among male students, senior students, and students from key universities, with digital learning evaluation competence emerging as a significant positive predictor of academic performance. (Ling (Angela) Xia1, 2024) stated that the transition to university is particularly demanding for students in English-medium instruction (EMI) settings, where academic work is conducted in a second language. Although ICT competence has been widely linked to academic success, less attention has been given to its relationship with language proficiency. A study of 1,742 first-year students at an EMI university in East China found that prior EMI experience and higher English proficiency were associated

with stronger ICT competence, highlighting the need for targeted support to help students develop both language and digital skills. (Putri Elia Angguni, 2026) explained that the digital literacy is increasingly important for EFL students in higher education, particularly in supporting academic writing. In their study of 66 postgraduate students at Yogyakarta State University found a very strong positive correlation between digital literacy and perceived academic writing ability ($r = 0.985$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that stronger digital skills may enhance students' writing confidence and academic performance. Moreover, Researcher Yulian Dinihari and others (2026) examined how digital literacy and Indonesian language proficiency influence social media use. Their findings showed that higher digital literacy was linked to more critical, self-regulated, and ethical online behavior, while stronger language proficiency supported clearer, more polite, and context-sensitive digital communication.

Research Aim

This study aims to assess students' level of digital competence using an internationally recognized framework to determine statistically how English language proficiency influences digital competence, and to identify the relationship between these two variables.

Research Objectives

The study seeks to evaluate students' digital competence across five internationally aligned dimensions and to empirically examine the factors that influence these competences, with particular emphasis on the role of English language proficiency. The specific objectives are to:

- assess students' competence levels in each dimension of digital competence;
- identify, through statistical analysis, the factors that influence each dimension;
- examine the relationships among the selected variables and determine the strength of their influence.

Research Methodology

The questionnaire was developed and administered through Microsoft Forms. Using random sampling, data were collected from 357 students at Mandakh University.

Research Design

Based on the theoretical framework discussed above, the research design of this study is structured as follows. In accordance with the research design, five sub-variables representing students' digital competence were identified based on international frameworks. These sub-variables were developed within a mixed theoretical framework informed by internationally recognized models, particularly DigComp 2.2 and the UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers (ICT-CFT). Gender, year of study, and information technology experience were included as control variables to examine potential group differences and relationships, as well as to determine the influence of English language proficiency on students' digital competence. The questionnaire items used to measure the

research variables were adapted from validated instruments proposed in previous international studies. Participants completed the survey through self-assessment, and their responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. After the data were organized and cleaned, factor analysis was conducted to examine the underlying structure of the variables. Regression analysis was then performed to identify the relationships between the independent and dependent variables and to determine the extent to which the selected factors influenced students' digital competence.

Research results

This study involved **357 undergraduate students, ranging from freshmen to seniors, at Mandakh University**. The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented below.

Table 1

Demographic information				
No	Students' year	Participants	Percentage	
1	Level of study	1st year	159	44.5%
		2nd year	48	13.4%
		3rd year	88	24.6%
		4th year	62	17.4%
2	Gender	Male	104	29.1%
		Female	253	70.9%

Before conducting factor analysis, the reliability of the survey instrument was examined. Prior to the main data collection, a pre-test was also conducted to improve the clarity, quality, and validity of the questionnaire. Regarding the applications used to overcome language barriers when students' English proficiency is insufficient for using digital devices, software, or online environments, 41% of respondents reported using Google Translate, while another 41% reported using ChatGPT. In comparison, 7% indicated that they used dictionaries for this purpose.

In terms of students' online activities, half of the respondents reported spending most of their time on social networking platforms such as Facebook and Instagram. This was followed by coursework and research-related activities at 23%, communication with friends through chat at 13%, watching videos on platforms such as YouTube at 11%, and playing online games at 3%. With respect to AI chatbot use, ChatGPT was the most frequently used application, reported by 85% of respondents. Gemini AI was used by 10%, while the remaining 5% reported using other AI chatbot applications.

Factor Analysis Results

Table 2

KMO and Bartlett's test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.959
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	5982.427
	df	300
	Sig.	.000

A KMO value of 0.959 demonstrates that the data have excellent suitability for factor analysis. Moreover, the significance value (Sig. = 0.000, $p < 0.05$) indicates that the result is statistically significant. Factor analysis was conducted for each of the five variables designed to measure students' current level of digital competence. Across the five factors, all questionnaire items demonstrated factor loadings above 0.60, while the KMO values exceeded 0.70. These results indicate that the sample was adequate and that the data were appropriate for factor analysis.

The Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranged from 0.829 to 0.905, indicating strong internal consistency and reliability among the items within each variable. Taken together, the factor analysis results suggest that the questionnaire was statistically reliable and demonstrated a high level of construct validity and internal consistency.

To further examine students' digital competence, the mean scores for each of the five dimensions were calculated. The results are presented below:

Table 3

Students' digital competence according to 5 dimensions

Statistics	Information and Data Literacy	Communication and Collaboration	Digital Content Creation	Digital Safety	Artificial Intelligence and Digital Ethics
Valid N	357	357	357	357	357
Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.7780	3.9797	3.7417	3.7348	3.8599

The descriptive statistics show that all five dimensions of digital competence had valid responses from 357 participants, with no missing data. Among the five dimensions, Communication and Collaboration had the highest mean score ($M = 3.9797$), followed by Artificial Intelligence and Digital Ethics ($M = 3.8599$) and Information and Data Literacy ($M = 3.7780$). Meanwhile, Digital Content Creation ($M = 3.7417$) and Digital Safety ($M = 3.7348$) showed comparatively lower mean scores. These results suggest that students demonstrated relatively stronger competence in communication and collaboration, while digital safety and digital content creation may require further development.

Regression Analysis

Digital competence was analyzed across five sub-dimensions: information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, digital safety, and artificial intelligence and digital ethics. For each sub-dimension, dummy variables were created for the selected influencing factors, and regression analysis was conducted using the least squares method. The purpose of this analysis was to determine which factors significantly influence each dimension of students' digital competence and to examine the explanatory power of these variables.

1. Factors Influencing Information and Data Literacy

Table 4

Factors Influencing Information and Data Literacy

No.	Regression analysis	Beta	t	Sig.	F	R ²	Result
1	Year/level of study →	0.028	0.742	0.459	91.839	0.505	Rejected
2	Gender →	0.090	2.401	0.017	91.839	0.505	Supported
3	English language proficiency →	0.146	3.840	0.000	91.839	0.505	Supported

The regression results show that the overall model was statistically significant, with an F-value of 91.839 and an R² value of 0.505. This indicates that the selected variables accounted for 50.5% of the variance in students' information and data literacy.

Among the predictors, students' year/level of study did not have a statistically significant effect on information and data literacy ($\beta = 0.028$, $p = 0.459$). Therefore, this factor was rejected. In contrast, gender ($\beta = 0.090$, $p = 0.017$), English language proficiency ($\beta = 0.146$, $p = 0.000$), and IT experience ($\beta = 0.672$, $p = 0.000$) were found to have statistically significant effects.

Among these factors, IT experience had the strongest influence on students' information and data literacy, as shown by the highest beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.672$). This suggests that students with greater experience in using information technology are more likely to demonstrate stronger competence in searching, evaluating, managing, and using digital information. English language proficiency also had a positive influence, indicating that students with better English skills may be better able to access and understand digital information, particularly in English-based online environments.

2. Factors Influencing Communication and Collaboration Skills

Table 5

Factors Influencing Communication and Collaboration Skills

No.	Regression analysis	Beta	t	Sig.	F	R ²	Result
1	Year/level of study →	-0.092	-2.101	0.459	44.112	0.326	Supported
2	Gender →	-0.008	-0.178	0.017	44.112	0.326	Rejected
3	English language proficiency →	0.204	4.584	0.000	44.112	0.326	Supported
4	IT experience →	0.505	11.315	0.000	44.112	0.326	Supported

The regression results show that the overall model was statistically significant, with an F-value of 44.112 and an R² value of 0.326. This means that the selected variables accounted for 32.6% of the variance in students' communication and collaboration skills.

Among the predictors, gender did not have a significant influence on communication and collaboration skills. Therefore, this factor was rejected.

In contrast, year/level of study, English language proficiency, and IT experience were found to have significant effects. Among these, IT experience had the strongest positive influence ($\beta = 0.505$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that students with more experience in using information technology tend to demonstrate stronger communication and collaboration skills in digital environments.

English language proficiency also had a positive effect ($\beta = 0.204$, $p = 0.000$), suggesting that students

with higher English proficiency may communicate and collaborate more effectively through digital tools. Year/level of study showed a negative coefficient ($\beta = -0.092$), which suggests that higher-year students may show slightly lower communication and collaboration

scores compared with lower-year students, depending on how the variable was coded.

3. Factors Influencing Digital Content Creation Skills

Table 6

Factors Influencing Digital Content Creation Skills

No.	Regression analysis	Beta	t	Sig.	F	R ²	Result
1	Year/level of study →	0.057	1.495	0.136	85.765	0.488	Rejected
2	Gender →	0.090	2.345	0.020	85.765	0.488	Supported
3	English language proficiency →	0.098	2.542	0.011	85.765	0.488	Supported
4	IT experience →	0.672	17.275	0.000	85.765	0.488	Supported

The regression results indicate that the overall model was statistically significant, with an F-value of 85.765 and an R² value of 0.488. This means that the selected variables accounted for 48.8% of the variance in students' digital content creation skills. Students' year/level of study did not have a statistically significant effect on digital content creation skills ($\beta = 0.057$, $p = 0.136$). Therefore, this factor was rejected.

In contrast, gender ($\beta = 0.090$, $p = 0.020$), English language proficiency ($\beta = 0.098$, $p = 0.011$), and IT experience ($\beta = 0.672$, $p = 0.000$) were found to have significant effects. Among these factors, IT experience had the strongest influence, as shown by the highest beta coefficient. This suggests that students with greater information technology experience are more likely to demonstrate stronger skills in creating digital content.

4. Factors Influencing Digital Safety Skills

Table 7

Factors Influencing Digital Safety Skills

No.	Regression analysis	Beta	t	Sig.	F	R ²	Interpretation
1	Year of study →	-0.042	-0.977	0.329	46.511	0.338 ^a	Rejected
2	Gender →	0.123	2.840	0.005	46.511	0.338 ^a	Supported
3	English language proficiency →	0.146	3.309	0.001	46.511	0.338 ^a	Supported
4	ICT experience →	0.542	12.247	0.000	46.511	0.338 ^a	Supported

The regression results show that the overall model was statistically significant, with an F-value of 46.511 and an R² value of 0.338. This indicates that the selected variables accounted for 33.8% of the variance in students' digital safety skills.

Students' year/level of study did not have a statistically significant effect on digital safety skills ($\beta = -0.042$, $p = 0.329$), so this factor was rejected. In contrast, gender ($\beta = 0.123$, $p = 0.005$), English language proficiency ($\beta = 0.146$, $p = 0.001$), and IT experience

($\beta = 0.542$, $p = 0.000$) had statistically significant effects.

Among these predictors, IT experience had the strongest influence on digital safety skills. This suggests that students with greater experience in using information technology are more likely to demonstrate stronger awareness and ability in protecting personal data, using digital tools safely, and managing risks in online environments.

5. Factors Influencing Artificial Intelligence and Digital Ethics Skills

Table 8

Factors Influencing Artificial Intelligence and Digital Ethics Skills

No.	Regression analysis	Beta	t	Sig.	F	R ²	Result
1	Year/level of study →	-0.056	-1.261	0.208	40.319	0.306	Rejected
2	Gender →	0.069	1.549	0.122	40.319	0.306	Rejected
3	English language proficiency →	0.160	3.552	0.000	40.319	0.306	Supported
4	IT experience →	0.511	11.294	0.000	40.319	0.306	Supported

The regression results show that the overall model was statistically significant, with an F-value of 40.319 and an R² value of 0.306. This indicates that the selected variables accounted for 30.6% of the variance in students' artificial intelligence and digital ethics skills.

Students' year/level of study ($\beta = -0.056$, $p = 0.208$) and gender ($\beta = 0.069$, $p = 0.122$) did not have statistically significant effects; therefore, these factors were rejected. In contrast, English language proficiency

($\beta = 0.160$, $p = 0.000$) and IT experience ($\beta = 0.511$, $p = 0.000$) were found to have significant positive effects.

Among the predictors, IT experience had the strongest influence, suggesting that students with greater experience in using information technology are more likely to demonstrate stronger competence in using AI tools responsibly and understanding digital ethics. English language proficiency also had a positive effect, indicating that better English skills may support

students' ability to access, understand, and apply AI-related information and ethical guidelines in digital contexts.

Conclusion

This study assessed students' digital competence using an internationally informed mixed framework. Within this framework, students evaluated their digital competence through a self-assessment questionnaire. Factor analysis was conducted to identify and validate the key dimensions of digital competence.

First, the findings indicate that students generally evaluated their digital competence at a moderate to good level. Specifically, **65.4%** of respondents rated their information and data literacy as good or very good, **73.63%** rated their communication and collaboration skills as good or very good, **64.14%** rated their digital content creation skills as good or very good, **63.07%** rated their digital safety skills as good or very good, and **69.7%** rated their artificial intelligence and digital ethics skills as good or very good. Among the five dimensions, communication and collaboration received the highest rating, while digital safety received the lowest. Overall, students' average digital competence level was **67.19%**, corresponding to a mean score of **3.82**.

Second, students' self-assessed English proficiency varied across levels: **28.6%** reported beginner-level proficiency, **60.8%** reported intermediate-level proficiency, and **10.7%** reported advanced-level proficiency. Regression analysis showed that English proficiency was significantly associated with all five dimensions of digital competence. This suggests that students with higher English proficiency are more likely to learn, access, and use digital tools effectively. In addition, stronger English skills may help students overcome challenges related to digital technology use, even when their digital competence is still developing.

Third, the survey results further support the importance of English proficiency in developing digital competence. A majority of students (**59.7%**) reported that English proficiency has a strong influence on their digital competence development, while **34.7%** reported a moderate influence and **5.6%** reported a low influence. However, students' ability to understand and use English-language software instructions, learning materials, and web resources appeared to be limited. Only **3.9%** reported that they could fully understand and use such resources, while **34.7%** could understand and use them most of the time, **43.7%** could use them with partial understanding, and **17.6%** could understand and use them only occasionally. These findings suggest that limited English proficiency may remain a barrier to students' effective use of digital resources.

Finally, the regression results confirmed that both English language proficiency and information technology experience significantly influenced all five dimensions of digital competence: information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, digital safety, and artificial intelligence and digital ethics. Therefore, improving students' English proficiency and providing more opportunities for practical technology use may contribute to strengthening their overall digital competence.

Recommendations

The findings indicate that information technology experience is a significant factor in strengthening students' digital competence. Therefore, the current information technology curriculum should be carefully reviewed and improved to better support the development of students' digital skills. In particular, topics related to digital safety, artificial intelligence, and digital ethics should be systematically integrated into the course content.

The results also show that English language proficiency plays an important role in students' digital competence. Although 60.8% of students rated their English proficiency as intermediate and 28.6% as beginner level, their ability to use English-language learning materials and web-based resources remained moderate. This suggests that limited English proficiency may restrict students' ability to access, understand, and effectively use digital tools and online resources.

Therefore, future curriculum development should place greater emphasis on improving students' English language skills, especially in relation to digital learning contexts. Strengthening students' ability to understand English-language software instructions, online learning materials, and web-based information may contribute to the improvement of their overall digital competence.

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